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Analysis of Ghanaian Political Sentiments using Deep Learning and Machine Learning Approaches

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decade, with the growth of social media platforms such as Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook, the volume of data gathered from users worldwide has increased substantially, leading to the publishing and collecting of micro-opinion pieces. These help people modify or document their feelings about objects, individuals, and events. Most political parties in Africa use the Twitter platform to communicate. This paper attempts to mine tweets, capture political sentiments, and analyze them by performing deep learning and machine learning models on the tweets. Specific hashtags are used to aid the collection of tweets. The extraction of tweets about the Ghanaian Government and Elections is carried out along with the study of sentiments among Ghanaian Twitter users towards the current government of Ghana to predict its faith in the next general elections. Subsequently, the performance of the deep learning and machine learning approaches will be evaluated.

Keywords

Twitter, tweets, sentiments, SVM, Naïve Bayes, LSTM

Introduction

The number of web 2.0 resources like e-commerce and social media where people are comfortable sharing thoughts and ideas have evolved tremendously, and vast amounts of data are produced due to this increase [13]. As a result, sentiment analysis has automatically extracted meaningful information from these vast datasets. Sentiment analysis is a branch of natural language processing (NLP) that attracts a lot of interest from academics, businesses, and government agencies across the world. Sentiment analysis, also known as sentiment mining or opinion mining, is a method for determining the emotional tone of a group of words. This assessment helps to understand the impression, perspective, or emotion expressed. A target, an item or a feature of an entity, and a mood (positive, negative, or neutral) are all components of Liu's definition of an opinion. It may also include the source of the viewpoint and the date and time the view was expressed. Sentiments are classified into various groupings depending on the classification goal [1].

Tweets are classified as "friendly," "unfavorable," or "neutral." Sites such as Twitter are a social media platform where many opinions or sentiments are registered, many of which provide helpful information. Traditional approaches have attained significant levels of precision, but the feature engineering needed is time-consuming and complex [14]. The enormous amounts of user-generated data nowadays need comprehensive understanding and dependable methods for its management. As a result of its capacity to learn from data sets without necessitating a manual attribute selection procedure, deep learning approaches enable the establishment of computational models. As previously indicated, in March 2014, active Arabic users tweeted more than 20 million tweets every day. Millions of tweets are sent out every minute, many in their native tongues. Twitter is often used to discuss diverse topics such as health, entertainment, sports, politics, technology, education, and other issues. There have been a lot of different techniques for sentiment analysis. Lexicon-based, as well as machine learning-based methods, are the two sorts of traditional procedures. Machine learning techniques form models from labeled examples of viewers or sentences [8]. This paper uses machine learning and deep learning algorithms to classify tweets collected from Twitter, using Naïve Bayes and SVM machine learning algorithms and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN).

Related Works

Natural language processing (NLP), text analytics, and computational linguistics face sentiment analysis challenges. Sentiment analysis shows how people feel about the thing or subject under discussion in its broad sense. Its first application assessed sentiment in long texts like emails and letters. It is also used in criminal activity analysis, both before and after the fact [5]. This topic of study has recently risen to prominence because of the development of online applications like microblogging websites, chat groups, and social networking sites. People use this software to analyze, remark on, and criticize numerous issues and create reviews, suggestions, and other types of content. User-generated data contains a lot of knowledge about goods, individuals, events, and other topics. The current world's harsh competition has resulted in complex feedback from customers and satisfaction-to-innovation cycles [13]. Because crowd-sourced processing and analysis are complex, vast amounts of user-generated information necessitate the employment of automated systems for mining and analysis. In recent times, many individuals have conducted extensive research on "Sentiment Analysis on Tweets" [4]. It was initially intended for primary classification, which assigns opinions and feedback to one of two bipolar classifications: positively or negatively [10]. Proposed a three-category classification system for Twitter messages: objective, positive, and negative. They created a Twitter database by using the data from Twitter to annotate Twitter posts with emoticons automatically. They used that dataset to develop a classification model based on the multinomial Naive Bayes technique, which uses characteristics like Ngram and POS-tags. The training set was less effective because it only comprises tweets with emoticons [8]. [9] utilized a Naive Bayes bigram technique with a Maximum Entropy method to classify tweets. [1] According to the researchers, the Naive Bayes classifiers surpassed the Maximum Entropy Method. They were using their test dataset of Twitter posts with emoticons acting as chaotic tags, [6] proposed indirect monitoring to perform sentiment analysis for Twitter messages. They use Naive Bayes, MaxEnt, and Support Vector

Machines (SVM) to create their models. Unigrams, bigrams, and point-of-sale (POS) were part of their feature space. They concluded that SVM outperformed other algorithms and that unigrams worked better as features. [2] developed a two-phase automated text analysis approach for categorizing tweets. Machine learning algorithms are used in the majority of sentiment analysis research. The messages in the sentiment analysis field can be favorable or unfavorable [3]. Positivity, negativity, and neutral are all examples of multi-valued or binary categories (or irrelevant). Although the class quantity in sentiment analysis is much less than that in the subsequent technique of another topic-based cataloging, the non-usability of keywords is the fundamental complexity of text categorization in sentiment analysis [12]. Before, As previously stated, conventional sentiment analysis methods were the first to converge. Traditional techniques are divided into lexicon-based methods and machine learning methods. Deep learning is a fast-expanding topic in machine learning approaches based on self-learning artificial neural networks (ANNs) inspired by the biological brain. The web is made up of dozens to hundreds of layers, each of which receives and analyzes data from the one before it, allowing for multiple processes [7]. For example, the computer will learn to recognize letters before focusing on words in a text or determine whether an image contains a face before identifying who it belongs to. Due to their ability to autonomously learn and produce input models from sets of data, deep learning methods have mainly been employed in sentiment analysis [4]. Recent research has shown that deep learning may be used to perform sentiment analysis in various methods, including supervised and unsupervised techniques.

Materials and methods

Data Acquisition

Twitter returns a collection of tweets that match a specified query using a standard API. This API provides historical tweets published up to 7 days that match a predefined query (the keyword, mention, hashtag, etc. that you'd like to search) [4]. Unlike real-time analysis, you are retrieving information from the past in this case. While the Standard Search API is free, it has a 7-day limit. The alternatives are paid historical search APIs (like Historical PowerTrack and Full-Archive Search), which provide access to the last 30 days of tweets or even tweets from early as 2006. The application was made for the standard API, and permission was granted to access the standard API for some period to extract tweets related to the subject for this study. Python was used as a tool to write a script that allows connecting to the Twitter Standard Search API. The collected tweets are prominently significant to sentiments of the governance of the current and the main opposition party. Historical tweets from 7 days ago containing a specific keyword, hashtag, or mention, were collected and saved into a CSV file.

#GhanaElection OR #4MoreForNana OR #4MoreToDoMoreForYou OR #NDCDecides OR #YearOfRoads were the keywords and hashtags used. The tweets were saved under the following column categories: Tweet content (text of the tweet), Date (date and hour of the tweet), User (name of the author of the tweet), source used to post the tweet (for example, Twitter Web Client or Buffer), Tweet ID, and Tweet URL.

Data Preprocessing

Twitter has distinct conventions as compared to other online social media text, due to which special care is taken during the cleaning and preprocessing of raw tweets. Over 3,000 tweets were preprocessed to convert tweets to lower case, remove twitter username, remove punctuations, numbers, and special characters. And also, convert more than two-letter repetitions to two letters example woowooow to woow. The next preprocessing task was to remove extra spaces, remove urls, emoji analysis, handle contractions words such as " can't " to " cannot, "" won't " to " will not ", and "shouldn't" to " should not " and finally remove Stop words. Out of the 3,000 tweets, 1753 were prepared for sentiment classification after the cleaning and annotation phases.

Fig.1 The prior distribution of the sentiment tweets.

Machine learning classification models

Naïve Bayes Model: The Naive Bayes algorithm is based on Bayes' theorem, a probabilistic approach for estimating event likelihoods using conditional probabilities. There are two commonly used models, i.e., multinomial and multi-variate Bernoulli models for using Naïve Bayes approaches. The multinomial model is adopted in this paper.

$$P(A|B) = P(B|A) * P(A) / P(B) \quad (1)$$

The posterior probability of the event $P(A|B)$ is termed the prior probability, while the marginal probability of the event $P(A)$ is called the posterior probability.

Support Vector Machine or SVM: The SVM is a popular Supervised Learning method that may solve both classification and regression issues. However, it is primarily utilized in Machine Learning for Classification difficulties. SVM investigates information, characterizes choice limits, and uses the components for the calculation performed in the input space. Support vector machines represent an extension to nonlinear models of the generalized portrait algorithm developed by Vladimir Vapnik.

The SVM identifies a separating hyper-plane with optimality between the two classes of a training dataset. The hyper-plane obtains this optimum separation with the largest distance from the nearest training dataset.

$$w = \sum_j \alpha_j c_j d_j, \alpha_j \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

w is a vector that represents the hyperplane. $c_j \in \{-1, 1\}$ (-1 for negative, 1 for positive) is the correct calls of tweets d_j . α_j 's are obtained by solving a dual optimization problem.

Deep Learning Classification Model

Recurrent Neural Network (RNN): RNN is a neural network designed to analyze data streams using hidden units. It is mainly used in text processing, speech recognition, and DNA sequences, and the output depends on the previous computations. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). Long short-term memory (LSTM) units are units of a recurrent neural network (RNN) capable of learning long-term dependencies. An LSTM network is an RNN composed of LSTM units. Short-term memory is a problem for recurrent neural networks. They'll have difficulty transporting information from earlier time steps to later ones if the sequence is long enough. For example, if you're trying to predict something from a paragraph of text, there's a good chance RNNs will leave out essential information right at the start. Therefore, LSTMs and GRUs were created to solve short-term memory. They have internal mechanisms called gates that can regulate the flow of information.

Classification of Performance Evaluation

In a classifier, there is always something called a False Statement. For example, a sentence is declared negative even though the sentence is a positive sentence, or a sentence is declared neutral even though the sentence is a positive or negative sentence and a positive sentence that is declared negative (See Table 1). To avoid this, we must perform a performance evaluation to find the False Statement [11].

Table 1. Classification of Performance Evaluation

Classifier Categories	Positive	Negative
Positive	True positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
Negative	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

To find how much success an algorithm is, it is essential to check for accuracy using the formula below:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FN+FP+TN} \quad (3)$$

Precision is the ratio of the relevant items selected to all selected items. Precision can be interpreted as a match between the request for information and the answer to the request.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (4)$$

A recall is the ratio of relevant items selected to the number of relevant items available. A recall is calculated by:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (5)$$

Results and Discussions

The data used in this study is data from social media Twitter with comments on discussions about the current Ghanaian government and the opposition party. The keyword used is using a hashtag that is within the scope of the case discussed. The data used are relevant data that has been cleansed. The data is labeled as positive and negative sentiments. The data used in this study are tweets of Ghanaian people on Twitter that are taken using Python, then saved into CSV format files. Keywords for searching comments using hashtags and query searches are related to Ghanaian ruling party case studies. The data used are data that are relevant to the case studies discussed. The results of relevant data collected were 1753 tweets. The training and testing data ratio is 70:30, where 70% of the data was used as training data, and 30% was used as testing data. Table 4 presents the distribution of training data and testing data.

Table 2. Data training and Data testing distribution

	Training Data	Testing Data	Total
Amount of Data	1227	526	1753

Table 3 Result Classification of Performance Evaluation Naïve Bayes Classifier.

Classification Categories	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	Precision	Recall	F1 Measure
Prediction Positive	212	8	85	88	86
Prediction Negative	17	289	87	83	85

From the results of the table above, data with 526 tweets obtained 212 comments declared true positive, 289 comments declared true negative. From that result, the average percentage of Recall, Precision, and F1-Measure is 85%. The Naïve Bayes algorithm testing in this study produced an accuracy of 89.%. The computational time of this algorithm is about 10.22 seconds.

Table 4 Result Classification of Performance Evaluation SVM Classifier.

Classification Categories	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	Precision	Recall	F1 Measure
Prediction Positive	172	11	75	79	78
Prediction Negative	0	323	77	76	75

From the results of the table above, data with 526 tweets obtained 172 comments declared true positive, 323 comments declared true negative. From that result, the average percentage of Recall, Precision, and F1-Measure is 75%. Therefore, the SVM algorithm testing in this study produced an accuracy of 85%. The computational time of this algorithm is about 15 seconds.

Table 5 Result Classification of Performance Evaluation RNN (LSTM) Algorithm.

Classification Categories	True Positive (TP)	True Negative (TN)	Precision	Recall	F1 Measure
Prediction Positive	164	12	96	98	96
Prediction Negative	6	344	99	97	95

From the results of the data in the table above, data with 526 tweets obtained 164 comments declared true positive, 344 comments declared true negative. From that result, the average percentage of Recall, Precision, and F1-Measure is 98%. The LSTM classifier testing in this study produced an accuracy of 99% with a loss of 89%. The computational time of this algorithm is about 0.97 seconds.

Fig.2 Comparisons of classifiers

Table 7. Comparing Performance Results

Classifier	Accuracy %	Runtime (sec)
Naïve Bayes	89	10.22
SVM	85	15
LSTM	99	0.97

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